

Wind turbine defect detection using deep learning

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Article Info

Article history:

Received Oct 5, 2024

Revised Apr 11, 2025

Accepted May 6, 2025

Keywords:

Deep learning

Defect detection

Mean average precision

Wind energy

YOLOv8

ABSTRACT

Wind turbines play a critical role in the generation of renewable energy, but their maintenance and inspection, especially in large-scale wind farms, present significant challenges. Traditionally, wind turbines have been inspected manually, a process that is not only time-consuming but also costly and risky. Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have emerged as an efficient alternative, offering a safer and more economical means of gathering inspection data. However, the challenge lies in the manual analysis of the collected data, which demands expertise and considerable time. This paper proposes using object detection algorithms, specifically YOLOv8, to automate the detection of wind turbines and their defects, streamlining the inspection process. The model is trained on wind turbine images to identify potential faults such as cracks and corrosion. This approach aims to increase the accuracy and efficiency of wind turbine maintenance, ensuring prompt defect detection and reducing both operational costs and downtime.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Wind energy is a rapidly growing sector in the renewable energy landscape, playing a critical role in reducing carbon emissions and promoting sustainable energy generation [1]-[3]. Wind turbines are key assets in this domain, but their complex structures and constant exposure to harsh environmental conditions make them prone to damage. Regular inspection and maintenance of wind turbines are essential to ensure their operational efficiency and prevent unexpected failures. Traditional inspection methods, such as manual climbing or using ground-based equipment, pose several challenges, including safety risks, high costs, and limited detection accuracy [4]-[7]. As such, innovative solutions are needed to improve the efficiency and safety of wind turbine maintenance operations.

Unmanned aerial vehicles (UAVs) have emerged as an innovative tool for wind turbine inspection. UAVs can fly close to turbine structures, capturing high-resolution images of blades, towers, and nacelles, even in challenging locations that are difficult for humans to reach [8]-[10]. This technology allows for safer, faster, and more comprehensive inspections compared to traditional methods. However, as noted by Lei *et al.* [1], while UAVs can collect a significant amount of visual data, the manual review of this data is still time-consuming and requires expert analysis to identify potential issues, such as cracks or corrosion on

turbine blades. The need for automating this process has led to the exploration of advanced algorithms in machine learning and computer vision [11]-[13].

Fault diagnosis using machine learning algorithms is gaining traction in wind energy research. For instance, Qu *et al.* [2] developed a fault detection system based on fuzzy logic for turbines, demonstrating the potential of AI-driven techniques in this field. Similarly, the study by Rezaei *et al.* [3] employed modal-based damage identification to address nonlinearities in wind turbine blades. While these studies primarily focused on the mechanical aspects of wind turbines, they highlight the growing role of AI in predictive maintenance and fault detection [14]-[19]. Building on these concepts, integrating object detection algorithms into UAV-based wind turbine inspection offers the potential to automate the identification of structural defects, thus reducing human intervention.

Object detection models, such as the You Only Look Once (YOLO) series, have revolutionized real-time object detection by providing fast and accurate results. YOLOv8, the latest iteration, combines speed with improved detection accuracy, making it suitable for applications like wind turbine defect detection. According to Sun *et al.* [4], identifying damage in turbine blades using advanced machine learning techniques can significantly enhance maintenance processes by pinpointing issues early. Leveraging YOLOv8 in this context could automate the detection of critical defects, such as cracks, corrosion, or blade misalignments, based on the visual data captured by UAVs, thus improving the efficiency of turbine inspections [20]-[23].

Recent advancements in AI, particularly in the fields of object detection and anomaly detection, have shown promising results in wind turbine maintenance. Wang *et al.* [5] proposed a two-stage anomaly detection model to enhance fault detection in wind turbines, illustrating the benefits of combining machine learning with real-time monitoring systems. By training object detection algorithms like YOLOv8 on wind turbine images, it becomes possible to automate the identification of common issues such as blade damage or structural wear. This approach not only reduces the time and expertise required for manual inspections but also increases the overall reliability of the maintenance process.

Several previous studies have explored the integration of drone technology and computer vision for turbine inspection. For example, Foster *et al.* [10] demonstrated the potential of drone footage for detecting surface damage on turbines, showing the effectiveness of UAVs in capturing relevant data. However, the application of cutting-edge object detection models like YOLOv8 for this specific task is still in its early stages, making it a promising area of research. By refining these algorithms for wind turbine inspection, operators can achieve higher precision and better maintenance outcomes, leading to reduced downtime and enhanced energy output [24]-[25].

In summary, UAV-based inspection, combined with advanced object detection algorithms like YOLOv8, offers a powerful solution to the challenges associated with traditional wind turbine maintenance. This paper seeks to explore the potential of YOLOv8 in automating the defect detection process for wind turbines. By leveraging recent developments in AI and drone technology, this approach could significantly reduce the time, cost, and safety risks involved in turbine inspection, while improving the reliability of renewable energy generation.

2. METHODOLOGY

The object detection system for wind turbines was implemented using the YOLOv8 algorithm. The dataset consisted of wind turbine images with various defects, including cracks and surface corrosion. The images were annotated to define the bounding boxes around turbine components and labeled for defect types. The dataset was divided into training, validation, and testing sets, with a focus on training YOLOv8 to detect defects efficiently.

The YOLOv8 model was configured using pre-trained weights and fine-tuned on the wind turbine dataset. The data preprocessing included resizing images to a standard size to ensure compatibility with the YOLO architecture, while maintaining the aspect ratios of the turbine components. Data augmentation techniques, such as random rotation, flipping, and scaling, were applied to increase the variability of the training set and improve model robustness.

The training process utilized a batch size of 1 and a learning rate optimized through grid search. The model was trained for five epochs with a GPU accelerator to speed up computations. YOLOv8's architecture, which consists of convolutional layers and anchor-based detection, enables it to quickly identify objects in real time. After training, the best-performing model was saved and evaluated using the validation dataset to measure its performance metrics, including precision, recall, and mean average precision (mAP).

The evaluation metrics provided insights into the model's ability to accurately detect wind turbine defects. A confusion matrix was generated to assess the false positives and false negatives in defect detection. The final model was deployed for inference on the test dataset to evaluate its real-world applicability and effectiveness in detecting turbine defects. The object detection system for wind turbine defect identification

using YOLOv8 involves several key steps, each enhanced by mathematical formulations and data-driven optimization techniques. Figure 1 shows the flowchart of proposed method.

Figure 1. The flowchart of proposed method

- Dataset collection: The dataset consists of high-resolution wind turbine images. Let I represent the image set, where each image I_i . I is an array of pixel values. The images contain defects such as cracks and corrosion, represented by bounding boxes $B_i = \{(x1, y1), (x2, y2)\}$ which are manually annotated.
- Image annotation: The images are annotated with bounding boxes B_i , and defect types are labeled as L_i . The labels are assigned to each bounding box such that $D = \{(B_i, L_i)\}$ where D is the dataset of defect-labeled bounding boxes.
- Data preprocessing: Each image I_i undergoes preprocessing. The resizing of images is crucial to ensure compatibility with YOLOv8's input size, represented by the transformation function:

$$I_i = \text{fresize}(I_i, h, w) \quad (1)$$

where h and w are the height and width of the resized image. The aspect ratio is preserved during this process. Preprocessing also includes normalization to scale pixel values between 0 and 1.

- Data augmentation: Data augmentation is applied to increase the variability of the training set. Augmentation techniques such as random rotations $R(\theta)$ and scaling $S(S_x, S_y)$, S are used, where:

$$I_i'' = S(S_x, S_y) \cdot R(\theta) \cdot I_i' \quad (2)$$

this enhances model robustness by creating diverse training examples from the original images.

- Model training: The YOLOv8 model is trained using a loss function L_i , which combines classification loss L_{class} , bounding box regression loss L_{bbox} , and object confidence loss L_{conf} . The total loss is given by:

$$L = \lambda_1 L_{\text{class}} + \lambda_2 L_{\text{bbox}} + \lambda_3 L_{\text{conf}} \quad (3)$$

where λ_1 , λ_2 , and λ_3 are hyperparameters that balance the contributions of each component. The training is performed using a batch size of 1 and an optimized learning rate η , which is fine-tuned using grid search.

- Model evaluation: The model is evaluated using performance metrics such as precision (P), recall (R), and mean Average Precision (mAP). Precision and recall are computed as:

$$P = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Positives}}$$

$$R = \frac{\text{True Positives}}{\text{True Positives} + \text{False Negatives}}$$

the mAP is calculated by averaging the precision over different recall levels.

- Inference on test data: The trained model is deployed for inference, where the bounding box predictions B_i and their corresponding confidence scores C_i are generated for each test image I_i . The detection is

considered successful if the intersection over union (IoU) between the predicted and ground-truth bounding boxes exceeds a threshold τ calculated as (4).

$$IoU = (|B_{pred} \cap B_{true}|) / (|B_{pred} \cup B_{true}|) \quad (4)$$

The final model's real-world applicability is assessed based on these metrics. The flowchart displayed outlines the complete process, from dataset collection to inference on test data, emphasizing each stage's role in the wind turbine defect detection system. This approach integrates mathematical equations at each stage to optimize the model's performance and ensure accurate defect identification. Figure 2 shows the visualized sample images with corresponding annotations.

Figure 2. Visualizing sample images with corresponding annotations

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The trained YOLOv8 model demonstrated strong performance in detecting defects on wind turbines with high precision and recall. The model achieved a train box loss of 0.04, which indicates that the predicted bounding boxes closely matched the actual defect locations. Similarly, the train class loss was reduced to 0.02, suggesting that the model was able to classify turbine defects accurately. These results indicate the effectiveness of YOLOv8 in identifying wind turbine defects from UAV-captured images. Figure 3 shows the training metrics and loss.

The model's performance was further evaluated using the mAP50 metric, which measures the average precision across different object categories at a 50% intersection over union (IoU) threshold. The model achieved an mAP50 score of 0.87, demonstrating its ability to accurately detect turbine defects across varying images. Additionally, the mAP50-95 score was recorded at 0.76, highlighting the model's robustness across a wide range of IoU thresholds, thus confirming its capability for accurate localization of defects.

One of the major challenges in wind turbine defect detection is distinguishing between false positives and true positives, especially in cases of small or subtle defects. By analyzing the confusion matrix, it was observed that the model had a false positive rate of 3%, which is acceptable given the complexity of turbine images. This low rate of false positives indicates that the model can reliably detect actual defects without over-predicting them.

The ability to deploy this object detection model in real-world scenarios was also explored. UAVs equipped with high-resolution cameras can capture large volumes of data across wind farms, and the YOLOv8 model can process these images in real time to identify potential defects. This system can help operators focus on turbines that require immediate attention, streamlining the maintenance process. The results suggest that this approach can significantly reduce inspection time and costs, allowing operators to optimize turbine performance and reduce downtime. Figure 4 shows the simulated output results.

Moreover, the model's ability to generalize across different wind turbine environments was tested by introducing new images from various wind farms. The YOLOv8 model demonstrated consistent performance, detecting defects even in images taken under different lighting conditions and perspectives. This flexibility highlights the practical utility of this system for diverse wind farm environments.

Figure 3. The training metrics and loss

Figure 4. The simulated output

4. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, the application of YOLOv8 for wind turbine object detection offers a promising solution to the challenges of maintaining and inspecting wind farms. The model's high accuracy and real-time detection capabilities can reduce the need for manual inspections, improving safety and reducing operational costs. Furthermore, this approach allows wind farm operators to quickly identify and address potential defects, ensuring continued optimal performance of turbines. With further improvements and integration into UAV systems, YOLOv8 can revolutionize wind turbine maintenance, promoting the wider adoption of renewable energy.

FUNDING INFORMATION

The authors confirm that the research was carried out independently without financial influence.

AUTHOR CONTRIBUTIONS STATEMENT

This journal uses the Contributor Roles Taxonomy (CRediT) to recognize individual author contributions, reduce authorship disputes, and facilitate collaboration.

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C : Conceptualization

M : Methodology

So : Software

Va : Validation

Fo : Formal analysis

I : Investigation

R : Resources

D : Data Curation

O : Writing - Original Draft

E : Writing - Review & Editing

Vi : Visualization

Su : Supervision

P : Project administration

Fu : Funding acquisition

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENT

Authors state no conflict of interest.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Raw data is not publicly available due to privacy or institutional restrictions.

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